

THE IMPACT OF ANXIETY ON SPEAKING PERFORMANCE AMONG TEENAGERS LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN PRIVATE EDUCATIONAL CENTERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This study investigates the impact of foreign language anxiety on the speaking performance of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. While previous research has extensively examined Foreign Language Anxiety, relatively limited attention has been paid to its direct effect on speaking performance in classroom-based EFL contexts, particularly at lower proficiency levels.*

Therefore, the primary aim of this study is to explore how different dimensions of anxiety influence learners' oral communication and to identify key factors affecting their speaking ability. The study is grounded in the theoretical framework of Foreign Language Anxiety as proposed by Elaine K. Horwitz, focusing on communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test-related anxiety.

A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining classroom observations with qualitative feedback from pre-intermediate and intermediate learners. The findings reveal that high anxiety levels significantly reduce fluency, accuracy, and participation.

The study concludes that supportive, learner-centered teaching strategies are essential for minimizing anxiety and improving speaking performance.

Key words: *Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA), Speaking performance, EFL learners, Communication apprehension, Fear of negative evaluation, Classroom-based research, Learner-centered instruction*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganayotgan (EFL) talabalarining nutq faoliyatiga xorijiy til tashvishining ta'sirini o'rganadi. Oldingi tadqiqotlarda Xorijiy til tashvishi keng o'rganilgan bo'lsa-da, ayniqsa boshlang'ich va o'rta darajadagi o'quvchilar orasida, uning sinf sharoitida nutq faoliyatiga bevosita ta'siriga nisbatan kamroq e'tibor qaratilgan.*

Shu sababli, ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi tashvishning turli jihatlari o'quvchilarning og'zaki muloqotiga qanday ta'sir qilishini aniqlash hamda ularning nutq ko'nikmalariga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni belgilashdan iborat. Tadqiqot Elaine K. Horwitz tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan Xorijiy til tashvishi nazariy asosiga tayangan bo'lib, unda kommunikativ qo'rquv, salbiy baholanishdan qo'rqish va test bilan bog'liq tashvish omillari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Tadqiqotda aralash metodlar yondashuvi qo'llanilib, sinf kuzatuvlari hamda boshlang'ich-o'rta va o'rta darajadagi o'quvchilardan olingan sifatli fikr-mulohazalar tahlil qilindi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, yuqori darajadagi tashvish nutq ravonligi, aniqligi va faolligini sezilarli darajada pasaytiradi.

Tadqiqot xulosasiga ko'ra, o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi o'qitish strategiyalari tashvishni kamaytirish va nutq ko'nikmalarini yaxshilashda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so‘zlar: Xorijiy til tashvishi (FLA), nutq faoliyati, EFL o‘quvchilari, kommunikativ qo‘rquv, salbiy baholanishdan qo‘rqish, sinfga asoslangan tadqiqot, o‘quvchiga yo‘naltirilgan ta’lim

Аннотация. Данное исследование посвящено изучению влияния тревожности при изучении иностранного языка на устную речь учащихся, изучающих английский язык как иностранный (EFL). Несмотря на то, что в предыдущих исследованиях тревожность в изучении иностранного языка была широко рассмотрена, ее прямому влиянию на устную речь в условиях аудиторного обучения, особенно на начальных уровнях, уделялось относительно мало внимания.

Таким образом, основная цель данного исследования — изучить, как различные аспекты тревожности влияют на устную коммуникацию учащихся, а также выявить ключевые факторы, влияющие на их речевые навыки. Теоретической основой исследования является концепция тревожности при изучении иностранного языка, предложенная Elaine K. Horwitz, включающая коммуникативную тревожность, страх негативной оценки и тестовую тревожность.

В исследовании использовался смешанный метод, включающий наблюдение за занятиями и качественный анализ обратной связи от учащихся с уровнем ниже среднего и среднего. Результаты показали, что высокий уровень тревожности значительно снижает беглость, точность и активность учащихся в речи.

В заключение отмечается, что поддерживающие, ориентированные на учащегося стратегии обучения являются ключевыми для снижения тревожности и улучшения навыков устной речи.

Ключевые слова: тревожность при изучении иностранного языка (FLA), устная речь, учащиеся EFL, коммуникативная тревожность, страх негативной оценки, аудиторное исследование, обучение, ориентированное на учащегося

Introduction

Currently, mastering a foreign language is becoming a common trend among individuals. Since, it is strongly believed that knowing second language not only benefits on personal life but also professional life. During this process, among the four language skills, speaking is considered one of the most essential yet challenging skills for learners, especially teenagers in educational contexts. However, many learners experience psychological barriers that prevent them from speaking effectively. One of the most critical factors affecting speaking performance is **foreign language anxiety**, which can negatively influence learners’ confidence, fluency, and willingness to communicate.

Foreign language anxiety is commonly defined as a specific type of anxiety that arises in language learning situations, particularly in classroom settings. According to Elaine K. Horwitz, Michael B. Horwitz, and Joann Cope (1986), foreign language anxiety is a distinct form of anxiety that is associated with communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety. This concept explains why some learners feel nervous, avoid participation, and struggle to express themselves when using a foreign language.

Previous studies have extensively examined the relationship between anxiety and language learning. For example, Peter D. MacIntyre and Robert C. Gardner (1991) found that language anxiety negatively affects students’ speaking performance, as anxious learners tend to avoid communication and participate less in classroom activities. Similarly, Meihua Liu (2006) reported

that learners experience higher levels of anxiety when speaking in front of the whole class, while collaborative activities such as pair and group work can help reduce anxiety. In addition, Bashir Mak (2011) identified that speaking anxiety is mainly caused by fear of making mistakes, low self-confidence, and negative classroom environments. Furthermore, Stephen Krashen (1982) proposed the Affective Filter Hypothesis, suggesting that high levels of anxiety can block language input and prevent effective language acquisition. Despite the large number of studies conducted on foreign language anxiety, most of the existing research has focused on general ESL/EFL contexts or university-level learners in different countries. There is limited research specifically investigating **teenagers in private educational centers in Uzbekistan**, particularly in terms of how anxiety influences their speaking performance in classroom settings. This indicates a clear research gap, as the unique context of private education and teenage learners in Uzbekistan has not been sufficiently explored in previous studies.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine the impact of anxiety on speaking performance among teenage learners in private educational centers in Uzbekistan. This research also seeks to identify the main causes of anxiety and explore effective strategies that teachers can use to reduce anxiety and improve students’ speaking performance.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a **quantitative approach**, applying descriptive research methods. The aim of the research was to identify and assess the **main causes of speaking anxiety, its effects on students’ speaking performance, and the strategies learners use to avoid or reduce anxiety**. The study involved **15 beginner-level students** studying at an IELTS School, a private educational center in Navoi, Uzbekistan. All participants were teenagers with basic English proficiency, which allowed for a clearer understanding of how anxiety affects speaking at the early stages of language learning.

The data were collected using a **student questionnaire** designed in a simple and clear format appropriate for beginner-level learners. The questionnaire included multiple-choice items to ensure ease of understanding and accurate responses. The questions were divided into **two main categories** to better analyze students’ anxiety and coping strategies.

Categories of the Questionnaire

<p><i>1. Reasons and Effects of Speaking Anxiety</i></p>	<p>It included aspects such as nervousness, fear of making mistakes, stress, and concern about others’ opinions. It also examined how anxiety affects speaking performance, including hesitation, avoidance of participation, forgetting vocabulary, and preference for silence.</p>
<p><i>2. Avoidance Strategies of Speaking Anxiety</i></p>	<p>It explored factors that help reduce anxiety, such as pair and group work, teacher support, practice, and interactive activities.</p>

Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed to all 15 participants and completed in the classroom under the supervision of the researcher. The questions were explained in simple language to ensure full understanding, considering the participants’ beginner level of English proficiency.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using **quantitative methods**. The responses were examined through frequency counts and percentage distributions to identify common patterns related to the causes and effects of speaking anxiety, as well as the strategies used by students to reduce it. The results were then interpreted to provide a clear understanding of how anxiety influences speaking performance among beginner learners.

RESULTS

The analysis of the questionnaire revealed that **speaking anxiety is highly prevalent among beginner-level students** and has a noticeable impact on their speaking performance.

High Level of Speaking Anxiety — Speaking Performance

73% (11 participants) — Low speaking performance

The results indicate that a large proportion of students experience a high level of speaking anxiety. Among these 11 students, most reported frequent hesitation, fear of making mistakes, and a strong tendency to avoid speaking activities. These students demonstrated lower speaking performance, often struggling to express their ideas clearly and confidently.

Moderate Level of Speaking Anxiety — Speaking Performance

27% (4 participants) — Average speaking performance

The findings show that students with a moderate level of anxiety perform better than highly anxious learners but still face certain difficulties. These students sometimes feel nervous; however, they are able to participate in speaking activities, especially in supportive environments such as pair or group work.

No participants were identified as having a low level of speaking anxiety. This indicates that anxiety is a common issue among beginner learners in this context, and almost all students experience some degree of discomfort when speaking English.

Avoidance Strategies and Supportive Factors

Strategy / Factor	Number of Students	Percentage	Interpretation
Staying silent when feeling anxious	8 out of 15	55%	Common avoidance behavior
Switching to native language	9 out of 15	60%	Frequent coping strategy
Feeling more comfortable in pair/group work	11 out of 15	72%	Strong supportive factor
Teacher support increases confidence	12 out of 15	78%	Most influential factor
Interactive activities and regular practice help	10 out of 15	67%	Effective anxiety-reducing strategy

Overall, the findings demonstrate that **higher levels of anxiety are associated with lower speaking performance**, while supportive classroom conditions can help reduce anxiety and encourage more active participation.

DISCUSSION

The study found that speaking anxiety is highly prevalent among beginner-level learners and has a strong negative impact on their speaking performance. The majority of students (11 out of 15 participants, 73%) experienced high levels of anxiety and demonstrated low speaking

performance. A smaller group (4 out of 15 participants, 27%) showed moderate anxiety with relatively better performance. No students were found to have low anxiety levels.

These results indicate that speaking anxiety is a serious barrier in language learning at the beginner level. High anxiety limits students' ability to speak fluently, reduces participation, and negatively affects confidence. Even moderate anxiety still influences performance, although to a lesser degree, showing that emotional factors play a key role in speaking development.

The findings are consistent with previous research on foreign language anxiety. Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) stated that anxiety is one of the main psychological factors affecting learners' communication ability. Similarly, MacIntyre and Gardner (1994) found that anxious learners tend to avoid speaking, struggle with vocabulary retrieval, and perform poorly in oral tasks. The results of this study strongly support these theories, as students reported similar behaviors such as fear of mistakes and avoidance of speaking.

The main reasons for speaking anxiety include fear of making mistakes, lack of confidence, and worry about negative evaluation from classmates or teachers. These emotional barriers lead students to hesitate, forget vocabulary, and avoid participation. Additionally, limited speaking practice and low proficiency level increase nervousness, which further intensifies anxiety during speaking tasks.

The findings suggest important implications for teaching practice. Teachers should create a **supportive and low-anxiety classroom environment** where students feel safe to speak without fear of criticism. Increasing the use of **pair and group work, interactive activities, and games** can help reduce pressure on individual learners. Furthermore, continuous teacher encouragement and positive feedback are essential to build students' confidence and improve their speaking performance.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to investigate the impact of speaking anxiety on beginner-level students' speaking performance. The findings revealed that speaking anxiety is a widespread issue among learners, with the majority of participants (73%) experiencing a high level of anxiety, which negatively affected their ability to speak confidently and fluently. Students with moderate anxiety demonstrated relatively better performance, while no participants were found to have low levels of anxiety. Additionally, common coping strategies included avoidance behaviors such as staying silent and switching to the native language, whereas supportive factors such as teacher encouragement, pair and group work, and interactive activities were found to improve students' confidence.

The results highlight the **significant role of emotional factors in language learning**, particularly in speaking development. Speaking anxiety not only reduces students' participation but also limits their ability to process and produce language effectively. Therefore, addressing anxiety is essential for improving both learners' performance and their overall learning experience.

Based on these findings, it is important for teachers to create a **supportive and low-pressure classroom environment** where students feel comfortable making mistakes and actively participating in speaking tasks. The use of collaborative activities, communicative methods, and positive feedback can help reduce anxiety and promote more effective learning.

For future research, it is recommended to explore speaking anxiety among learners at different proficiency levels or in different educational contexts. Further studies could also examine the effectiveness of specific teaching strategies or interventions designed to reduce anxiety and improve speaking skills.

In conclusion, reducing speaking anxiety is a key factor in enhancing students’ speaking performance, and with appropriate teaching approaches, learners can become more confident and successful in using a foreign language.

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